

DFG Statement on the Use of Generative AI Models for Text and Image Creation

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Generative artificial intelligence (generative AI) is an AI that is able to generate text, images, videos or other data using generative models in response to a prompt. Generative AI is used in a variety of industries, such as art, software development and healthcare [1]. The use of generative AI in science and research is of particular interest not only to scientists, but also to funding bodies.

In September 2023, the Executive Committee of the German Research Foundation (DFG) published a statement addressing the influence of generative models on the sciences and the DFG's funding behavior [2]. The reason behind this is the rapid development of generative models such as ChatGPT [3], LUMINOUS [4], Midjourney [5], DALL-E [6] or Stable Diffusion [7], to name just a few. These AI models are now generally accessible and are changing the daily working behavior of their users. In addition to fast access to information and the promotion of creativity, the use of such technologies contains risks that should not be ignored when using them.

For example, generative models are known to create so-called “hallucinations”. This means that these technologies may invent things that are complete nonsense or carry out incomplete or incorrect literature searches, which can significantly impair the quality of publications without control mechanisms. To address this problem, scientific publication media such as Springer Nature Journals are introducing new author guidelines to regulate the use of generative models [8]. The DFG statement is intended to provide guidance for researchers, applicants and those involved in the review and decision-making process when dealing with generative AI models.

Figure: This image was created by H. Fliegl using the Stable Diffusion online tool [7]. (March 2024)

Generative technologies can influence both the creation of texts and the visualization of research results in everyday scientific life. For example, this technology has already developed so rapidly that it is not clear whether texts and illustrations were created with the help of generative models or whether the scientific ideas described in the text were developed with the help of generative AI [2, 8]. It is therefore important to deal transparently with the creation of text and image content in order to ensure the quality of the research and to be able to evaluate the technologies appropriately. In view of the significant opportunities and development possibilities, the DFG by no means rules out the use of generative models in the scientific field. However, it is important to define clear framework conditions in order to guarantee the quality of the results while ensuring good scientific practice.

It is very important that the research process and the resulting findings are transparent and comprehensible. These basic principles of scientific integrity should also be followed when dealing with generative models. Scientists themselves are responsible for adhering to the basic principles of scientific integrity, whether or not they are using generative models. To maintain scientific integrity when publishing their results, researchers should state the purpose and the extent to which generative models were used.

Only responsible natural persons can appear as authors in scientific publications. They must ensure that the use of generative models does not infringe any third-party intellectual property rights and that no scientific misconduct occurs, for example in the form of plagiarism. For this reason, the use of generative technologies is rated neither positively nor negatively when submitting an application.

It should be emphasized that the use of generative models in the preparation of expert opinions is considered inadmissible with regard to the confidentiality of the review process. Documents provided for review are confidential and must not be used as input for generative models. The use of locally installed generative technologies, for example for plagiarism detection, is not discussed further.

The DFG will continue to monitor and evaluate current developments. To this end, the Senate working group "Digital Change" was established, which, for example, deals with overarching subject-specific issues relating to the application of generative models on an ongoing basis. In addition to this, the DFG Commission is planning to revise the rules of procedure for dealing with scientific misconduct. Here, the effects of the use of generative models in cases of scientific misconduct will be examined in more detail [2].

Take Home Message:

- The use of generative models is not discouraged. However, it should be done with care.
- Researchers remain fully responsible for the texts and images they produce and have the duty to ensure compliance with good scientific practice.
- It must be clear for which purpose a generative model was used.
- Generative models may be used for applications, but they must not be used to prepare expert reports.

Methods

This text was optimized with the help of DeepL Write [9] and Chat GPT [3], whereby each text passage was subsequently revised by the author. The cover image was created with Stable Diffusion [7]. Translations of German texts were generated with DeepL Translate [10] and then checked and revised.

References

- [1] Wikipedia, Generative artificial intelligence (March 2024), https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Generative_artificial_intelligence
- [2] Statement by the Executive Committee of the DFG on the influence of generative models for text and image creation on the sciences and the DFG's funding activities <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/289674/ff57cf46c5ca109cb18533b21fba49bd/230921-stellungnahme-praesidium-ki-ai-data.pdf>
- [3] Open AI, ChatGPT (version of March 2024), Large Language Model, <https://chat.openai.com/>
- [4] Aleph Alpha GmbH, LUMINIOUS (version of March 2024), Large Language Model, <https://app.aleph-alpha.com/>
- [5] Midjourney, Inc., Midjourney (version 5.2, June 2023), image generating AI, <https://www.midjourney.com/home>
- [6] Open AI, DALL-E (version 3, March 2024), image generating AI, <https://openai.com/dall-e-3>
- [7] Black Technology LTD, Stable Diffusion (version of March 2024), image generating AI, <https://stablediffusionweb.com/>
- [8] Tools such as Chat GPT threaten transparent science; here are our ground rules for their use, Editorial, Nature 613, 612 (2023), doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-00191-1>
- [9] DeepL SE, DeepL Write (March 2024), text optimizing AI, <https://www.deepl.com/write>
- [10] DeepL SE, DeepL Translate (March 2024), translation tool, <https://www.deepl.com/en/translator>